

How do speculation and hedging of derivative financial products affect corporate value?

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Abstract

As international financial markets become increasingly interconnected amid globalization and technological progress, factors such as interest rates, exchange rates and raw material prices often experience dramatic fluctuations, and corporate financial management is faced with many uncertainties. According to relevant literature, derivative financial products have the characteristics of both hedging and leverage. If used appropriately, enterprises can mitigate short-term shocks and maintain stable cash flow. However, some studies have pointed out that if management tends to engage in speculative transactions, it may increase risk-taking and lead to unexpected losses. Therefore, not all research results agree on the impact of derivative financial products on corporate value. This study takes Taiwan's non-financial listed companies from 2009 to 2023 as the observation object, explores whether the use of derivative financial products by companies for two different purposes, namely hedging and speculation, shows a specific correlation with corporate value, and examines the role that corporate governance mechanisms may play in this process. The data source for this study is Taiwan Economic Journal (TEJ), and the combined cross-sectional data were used for regression analysis. The empirical results show that when companies use derivative financial products for hedging, there is a positive correlation with the company's value; if companies take speculative actions, the impact on the company's value is negative, but this negative result is not stable and may be affected by other factors. In addition, companies with good governance quality tend to use hedging strategies. The positive impact of corporate governance on corporate value can also be explained in part by the operation of derivative financial products for hedging purposes (impact path). On the other hand, regardless of the purpose of the operation (hedging, speculation), the higher the degree of use of derivative financial products, the weaker the marginal benefit of EPS on corporate value.

Keywords: Derivative Financial Instruments, Hedging Strategy, Speculative Trading, Corporate Governance, Corporate Value

1. Introduction

Against the backdrop of a rapidly developing global economy, the risks faced by enterprises are becoming increasingly diverse and complex. Especially since the mid-to-late 20th century, the world economy has experienced several major shocks, including three oil crises and multiple financial turmoil. These events have prompted companies to gradually realize the importance of risk management to sustainable operations. As an important tool for modern corporate risk management, derivative financial products provide enterprises with more financial operating space due to their unique flexibility and leverage characteristics. This type of financial instrument can not only serve as an effective hedging mechanism to reduce the negative impact of market fluctuations on business operations, but also as a speculative tool for pursuing short-term high returns. This dual attribute of both defensive and offensive nature makes derivative financial products play an increasingly important role in contemporary corporate financial management. However, this commodity is highly complex and is accompanied by huge risks and uncertainties, which has triggered continuous discussion and in-depth research on its application in academia and business circles.

The Asian financial crisis in 1997 was a concentrated display of the fragility of the regional economic system, and many companies therefore re-evaluated their risk management strategies. According to a cross-national study by Bartram (2019), approximately 60.5% of companies in 47 countries around the world use at least one derivative financial product, indicating that such instruments have become an important part of corporate capital operations. The original intention of designing derivative financial products is to help companies avoid the risks brought about by market fluctuations. For example, through hedging, companies can reduce the negative impact of exchange rate, interest rate and raw material price fluctuations on their operating cash flow and profits (Geczy et al., 1997). The stability characteristics of hedging derivatives can effectively reduce capital market penalties caused by financial instability. However, the leveraged nature of derivatives also brings additional risks. Taking the Baoqiao interest rate swap contract incident, the China Aviation Oil incident and the subprime mortgage crisis as examples, these incidents exposed the potential losses that companies may face in the process of operating derivative products. These cases have further raised market doubts about the effectiveness of derivative financial products. Especially when companies use such instruments for non-hedging purposes, their risk exposure will be further increased.

In addition to its hedging function, derivative financial products are also used by some companies as speculative tools in the hope of obtaining high short-term returns through market fluctuations. Although speculative operations deviate from the core goal of risk management in theory, in practice some companies still choose to use such commodities to conduct high-risk operations. Stulz (1996) pointed out that managers may choose to engage in speculative operations in pursuit of their own interests or to improve short-term financial performance, and this behavior is potentially in conflict with the company's goal of maximizing long-term value. The risky nature of speculative behavior also makes investors and market analysts tend to be conservative in their evaluation of such companies, thereby reducing the company's value (Graham et al., 2005).

In the process of enterprises using derivative financial products, corporate governance is regarded as a key decision-making and supervision mechanism. As the core of corporate governance, the board of directors plays an important role when a company decides to take risk-averse or speculative actions (Zhang and Huang, 2001). According to agency theory, when ownership and management rights are separated, management may choose high-risk speculative behavior due to self-interest (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). At this time, an effective

corporate governance mechanism can reduce agency problems and avoid excessive speculation from damaging the long-term value of the enterprise. According to Bartram (2019), high-growth, larger companies and high-paid board members are more inclined to engage in risk-averse derivative operations, which suggests that corporate governance plays an important role in the choice between risk aversion and speculative behavior. In addition, the empirical research of Allayannis and Ofek (2001) pointed out that risk aversion can effectively reduce the company's risk exposure, improve cash flow stability, and thus enhance the company's value. On the contrary, speculative behavior that is not for risk hedging purposes may amplify the financial risks of a company and cause its valuation to decline in the capital market. Based on this, it can be inferred from the studies of Bartram (2019) and Allayannis and Ofek (2001) that the quality of corporate governance structure will also affect the company's decision on the use of derivative products. For example, companies with higher governance scores are generally more inclined to adopt a conservative risk-averse strategy, while companies with lower governance levels may choose speculative behavior to pursue short-term gains. Other related studies also support this argument (such as Zhao et al., 2023; Rehman et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2017). In summary, corporate governance not only affects the company's choice of derivative operations, but also further determines its ultimate impact on the company's value. The specific research topics are as follows:

1. Discuss the impact of companies' use of derivative products for hedging and speculation on company value.
2. Extended exploration of the impact of corporate governance on a company's decision to use derivative financial products.

2. Literature review

The influencing mechanism of corporate value has long been a core issue of concern to researchers, and the hedging and speculative use of derivatives is likely to affect changes in corporate value. Smith and Stulz (1985) pointed out that achieving profit stability through hedging behavior can reduce the cost of financial crises and thereby increase corporate value. Barton (2001) emphasized that if a company can reduce the volatility of its earnings, the relative value of earnings information will increase, investors will have more confidence in the signals conveyed by financial statements, and the market will have a stronger understanding of the company's future growth and stability. On this basis, while improving the quality of earnings through hedging, it also improves the evaluation benchmark of enterprises in the capital market. Nance et al. (1993) specifically pointed out that small-scale enterprises are vulnerable to economic turbulence, so maintaining cash flow stability through hedging will have a multiplier effect on their value enhancement, because such enterprises often face greater challenges in the process of external financing. Stable financial performance can effectively reduce capital costs and eliminate the problem of underinvestment. However, the increase in corporate value is not a straight line, nor does it rely solely on reducing earnings volatility. Although the model of Froot et al. (1993) supports that hedging strategies can bring additional cash flow to reduce the problem of underinvestment. Wang and Zheng (2013) showed from empirical evidence that lower capital expenditure decisions can be positively correlated with higher return on equity in the short term. This finding means that the effect of derivatives in enhancing corporate value must be considered in both investment strategy and the company's overall financial planning. If a company simply increases capital expenditure in pursuit of long-term growth, it may reduce return on equity in the short term. Therefore, the growth of a company's value must strike a balance between risk aversion, investment layout and rate of return. In addition to the above

considerations, there is also an interactive relationship between the internal hedging planning direction of the enterprise and the external environment such as regulatory requirements, market mechanisms, and business strategies. If researchers or practical decision makers need a more complete understanding of this link, it still needs to be supplemented by other research. Overall, the impact of derivative products on company value presents diverse and dynamic intertwined relationships. If companies can accurately grasp hedging strategies to reduce the uncertainty of profits and cash flows, and prudently make investment allocation and capital structure decisions, it will help to ultimately enhance the company's value. Therefore, this study proposes the following research hypothesis:

H1: Companies that use derivatives for hedging will have a positive impact on corporate value.

When exploring the strategies for using derivative products, in addition to the trade-off between hedging and speculative intentions, it is more important to clarify the multiple factors that influence the orientation of the strategy. Previous literature has shown that companies face multiple pressures such as financial constraints, underinvestment risks, capital expenditure decisions, and earnings volatility, and often use derivatives to reduce uncertainty, ease funding pressure, and ensure stable operations (Berkman and Bradbur, 1996; Nguyen and Faff, 2002;

Bartram et al., 2006). The analysis by Nance et al. (1993) and Froot et al. (1993) pointed out that the incompleteness of financial structure and external environment makes hedging an option for certain enterprises to control risks. This incentive is particularly obvious for small-scale enterprises or enterprises with limited financial resources, because a stable financial status can indeed retain growth opportunities for enterprises in the face of market fluctuations.

However, external market conditions, industry characteristics and regulatory environment undoubtedly affect the configuration choices of derivative products (Sahoo, 2017; Bartram et al., 2006). For example, if the industry in which a company operates faces high price volatility or sharp changes in exchange rates or interest rates, its demand for derivative hedging will be stronger. On the contrary, if external regulations are unclear about information disclosure and restrictions on derivative operations, and the cost of speculation is relatively low, it will be easier for companies to transform tools that originally stabilized risks into leverage means that increase risk exposure. However, these external and market structural factors are only the

background environment that affects the direction of derivatives operations. What really implements decisions and shapes the direction of execution is the internal checks and balances mechanism and control structure of the enterprise (Grima et al., 2016; Ru-Fang, 2009). Previous

studies have repeatedly mentioned that agency problems can easily lead to management deviating from the goal of maximizing shareholder interests (Jensen and Meckling, 1976), and even leading to managers engaging in speculative operations using derivatives (Zheng, 1999).

If there is a lack of internal mechanisms to curb this incentive, the positive functions of derivatives, no matter how obvious they are, may become speculative tools to enhance short-term personal interests. In this context, the quality of corporate governance has emerged as a key determinant. The degree of perfection of the governance structure will determine whether

the company can strictly lock in the use of derivatives to reduce profit volatility and stabilize cash flow through institutionalized supervision and balance mechanisms. The completeness and

execution of the corporate governance mechanism can make managers' decisions more transparent and rational. When the composition of the board of directors is highly independent, the supervision density is sufficient, and the information disclosure mechanism is sound, speculative operations cannot grow in the shadows and are effectively controlled (Chen, et al., 2017; Wang and Zhang, 2011). At this point, derivative products, whether in terms of position selection, leverage or trading strategy, have a better chance of returning to their original

intention, that is, to provide favorable conditions for diversifying risks, preventing financial crises and improving profit stability. In addition, if companies can properly integrate the interests of all stakeholders under the governance structure, incorporate hedging strategies into the overall business policy and continuously track the results, it will not only reduce the risks derived from the use of derivatives, but also strengthen investors' trust in the company, making it easier for the company's value to gradually increase in a virtuous cycle. This is consistent with previous literature showing that corporate governance mechanisms can affect the company's overall core competitiveness (Wu, 2006), that is, the determinants of derivative commodity strategies can be explained at the primary level by financial status, industry environment, external supervision and capital allocation needs. However, only by further considering corporate governance mechanisms can we truly understand why some companies are able to steadily increase their value through hedging strategies while others fall into speculative traps. Through the adjustment of ownership and control, the interests of managers and shareholders can be aligned, fundamentally improving the original intention and direction of the use of derivative products. Therefore, this study speculates that when corporate governance is better, management tends to reasonably use derivatives as hedging tools rather than implement high-risk speculative strategies. Therefore, this study proposes the following research hypothesis:

H2: Companies with better corporate governance tend to use derivatives for hedging rather than speculation.

3. Research Methods

3.1 Samples and Data Sources

The research subjects of this study are all listed and OTC companies in Taiwan within the time range, excluding financial and insurance stocks and those with incomplete variable data. The financial and insurance industries are excluded because derivative products are within their business scope and their industrial nature is different from that of general enterprises. The source of the consolidated data on the company's operations on derivative products is the Taiwan Economic Journal (TEJ) derivative product database, which aggregates the derivative product information entered by the company in the public information observation station in accordance with the prescribed format. The Taiwan Economic Journal has undergone several revisions. In the fifth edition, the reporting method was simplified and changed to a consolidated reporting method. There is no need to make separate announcements for hedging purposes. Therefore, the time period of this research is set from the fifth edition boundary of 2009 to 2023. After initially excluding financial and insurance stocks and samples with incomplete data, this study obtained 21,530 observations; further excluding companies not involved in derivative operations, the final sample was 6,072. Among them, there were 4,952 cases of companies operating for hedging purposes only, reflecting that most companies tend to use derivatives to stabilize cash flow or reduce market volatility; there were 522 cases with non-hedging purposes only, which was relatively small; and there were 598 cases with both hedging and non-hedging motives, indicating that some companies may adopt speculative strategies for some positions under different conditions.

3.2 Variable Definition

3.2.1 Company Value

This research project refers to Cao et al. (2009) to use Proxy Q to measure company value.

$$\text{Proxy } Q_{i,t} = \frac{(P_{i,t} \times N_{i,t}) + L_{i,t}}{BV_{i,t}}$$

$P_{i,t}$ =Closing price of company i in year t.

$N_{i,t}$ =Number of shares outstanding at the end of year t for company i.

$L_{i,t}$ =Book value of total liabilities of company i at the end of year t.

$BV_{i,t}$ =Book value of total assets of company i at the end of year t.

3.2.2 Derivatives speculation and hedging use

This research project will classify the two types of derivative financial products disclosed in financial reports, including the amounts of "for hedging purposes - compliant with hedge accounting" and "for hedging purposes - not compliant with hedge accounting", as those for hedging purposes, while the remaining derivative financial products are undertaken for speculative purposes. This study refers to Wang and Kao (2005) to calculate the amount of derivatives by the sum of the nominal amount of outstanding and settled contracts at the end of the period, and to classify derivatives into hedging purposes (HDER) and non-hedging purposes (NDER) according to their operational purposes and calculate the total amount to obtain the degree of utilization. Both variables are calculated by multiplying the ratio of the total assets at the beginning of the period by 100 and then adding 1 to take the log. The reason for adding 1 is to avoid the problem of not being able to take the logarithm when the nominal amount is zero. This transformation helps reduce the impact of extreme values and improves the robustness of model estimates. The calculation method is as follows:

1. $HDER = \text{Log}[(\text{Total amount of settled and outstanding derivative financial products for hedging purposes at the end of the period} / \text{Total assets at the beginning of the period}) * 100 + 1]$

2. $NDER = \text{Log}[(\text{Total amount of settled and outstanding derivative financial products for non-hedging purposes at the end of the period} / \text{Total assets at the beginning of the period}) * 100 + 1]$.

3.2.3 Governance

Ding (2008) divided the corporate governance mechanism into five dimensions: equity structure, board structure, company structure, and information disclosure quality and management style. Each dimension has 1 to 2 variables, a total of 9 variables. However, it is difficult to obtain data on the number of companies with long-term equity investments using the equity method, so it was revised to 8 variables. Please see the summary in Table 1. After calculating the values of each variable of the sample company, the median of each year is used to distinguish between high and low levels. The high level is given 1 point, and the low level is 0 point. After adding up the scores of the 8 variables, the corporate governance index is obtained. If the index score is higher, it means the corporate governance mechanism is better, otherwise it means the corporate governance mechanism is worse. Each Dimension has 1 to 2 variables, for a total of 8 variables, as summarized in Table 1. After calculating the values of each variable of the sample company, the median of each year is used to distinguish between high and low levels. The high level is given 1 point, and the low level is 0 point. After adding up the scores of the 8 variables, the corporate governance index is obtained. If the index score is higher, it means the corporate governance mechanism is better, otherwise it means the corporate governance mechanism is worse. The data for calculating corporate governance indicators come from the TEJ Corporate Governance Module.

Table 1. Definition of variables for corporate governance indicators

Dimensions	Definition	Corporate Index Score	Governance
Ownership Structure			
Managers' shareholding ratio	Shareholding ratio of internal managers or group managers	Above (below) the median, 1 point (0 point)	
Shareholding ratio of major shareholders	Shareholding ratio of the top 10 shareholders or those with a shareholding ratio greater than 5%	Above (below) the median, 1 point (0 point)	
Board Structure			
Board size	Director Seats	Above (below) the median, 1 point (0 point)	
Ultimate controller's personal board seat	The number of seats held by the ultimate controller as a director in his or her personal capacity	Below (above) the median, 1 point (0 point)	
Company Structure			
Reinvestment rate	Ratio of reinvestment to assets	Below (above) the median, 1 point (0 point)	
Information Disclosure Quality			
Big Four Accounting Firms Audit and Attestation	If the company is certified by one of the Big Four accounting firms, this variable is 1, otherwise it is 0.	If the variable is 1, give 1 point, otherwise 0 points	
Management Style			
Chairman and General Manager	If the company's chairman also serves as the general manager, this variable is 1, otherwise it is 0.	If the variable is 0, give 1 point, otherwise 0 points	
Internalization of Chairman or General Manager	If the ultimate controller (and his family members) serves as chairman or general manager, this variable is 1, otherwise it is 0.	If the variable is 0, give 1 point, otherwise 0 points	

3.2.4 Control Variable

Firm size is related to firm value (Lang and Stulz, 1994). According to Chow and Wong-Boren (1987), when a company has a higher debt ratio, it will increase the company's agency costs, thereby affecting the company's value. Therefore, this study uses the debt-to-equity ratio (LEV) to control differences in capital structure. As shown by Chow and Wong-Boren (1987), the channel that affects corporate value is agency costs, so the stock earnings deviation difference (DEV) is included to measure the company's core agency problem. The greater the

difference between stock control rights and earnings distribution rights, the greater the degree of deviation. The comprehensive index of corporate governance mechanism (GOV) is the sum of the virtual variables of the governance mechanism to measure the strength of the internal governance mechanism. The theoretical value of this index is between 0 and 8. The closer the value is to 8, the better the corporate governance mechanism is, and vice versa. Company size (SIZE) can be used as an alternative variable to compensate for the omitted variables. According to Allayannis and Weston (2001), companies with high growth opportunities are positively correlated with future profitability, indicating that companies with growth opportunities will have better profitability and higher company value in the future. Therefore, growth opportunities (GROWN) are included.

3.3 Research model

3.3.1 Basic model

This study adopts Ohlson (1995) as the empirical model. The use of derivative products for hedging purposes and non-hedging purposes is adopted, and then the profit is multiplied by it to test how the use of derivative financial products with different motivations affects the value relevance of earnings, so as to capture the impact of the use of derivative financial products for non-trading purposes and trading purposes on the company's value. This study regards companies in each year as independent samples (all subsequent models are the same), and the OLS regression model is as follows:

Proxy $Q_{i,t} =$

$$\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 HDER_{i,t} + \alpha_2 EPS_{i,t} + \alpha_3 DEV_{i,t} + \alpha_4 GOV_{i,t} + \alpha_5 SIZE_{i,t} + \alpha_6 LEV_{i,t} + \alpha_7 GROWN_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

Proxy $Q_{i,t} =$

$$\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 NDER_{i,t} + \alpha_2 EPS_{i,t} + \alpha_3 DEV_{i,t} + \alpha_4 GOV_{i,t} + \alpha_5 SIZE_{i,t} + \alpha_6 LEV_{i,t} + \alpha_7 GROWN_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

3.3.2 Extended model

In theory, companies with sound corporate governance mechanisms are more inclined to adopt prudent financial strategies. It is expected that companies with poor corporate governance mechanisms are more inclined to engage in speculative operations, increase financial risks, and thus have a negative impact on the company's value. This study refers to Bilyay-Erdogan et al. (2023) and establishes the following model:

$$HDER_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GOV_{i,t} + \beta_2 EPS_{i,t} + \beta_3 DEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_5 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_6 GROWN_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

$$NDER_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GOV_{i,t} + \beta_2 EPS_{i,t} + \beta_3 DEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_5 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_6 GROWN_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

4. Empirical Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables, company value (Proxy Q), with an average of approximately 1.38 and a range of 18.25, indicating that there are considerable differences in the overall market evaluation of the sample companies. In terms of independent variables, the motivation for using derivative financial products is that the mean value of hedging use (HDER) is about 0.82, the median is around 0.78, the range is between 0 and 3.31, and the standard deviation is about 0.68. In comparison, the mean value of non-hedging use (NDER) is only about 0.03, and the maximum value is 2.32, indicating that most companies tend to operate derivative products for hedging purposes; the median of non-hedging use is 0, which means that most sample companies hardly use derivative products for speculation or only undertake very small positions. The average difference between shareholding control rights and profit distribution rights is 7.22, but can be as high as 70.87, with a standard deviation of about 12.66. The control rights and profit rights of some companies are obviously divergent, which in theory will have potential impacts on decision-making quality and agency problems.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables

	EPS	DEV	GOV	GROWN	SIZE	LEV	HDER	NDER	Proxy Q
Mean	2.81	7.22	3.52	0.06	9.98	0.43	0.82	0.03	1.38
Median	1.67	1.33	3.00	0.04	9.85	0.44	0.78	0.00	1.16
Maximum	81.07	70.87	7.00	4.22	12.74	0.98	3.32	2.32	18.61
Minimum	-57.86	0.00	0.00	-103.28	8.25	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.36
Std. Dev.	5.53	12.66	1.34	1.34	0.69	0.17	0.68	0.17	0.77

4.2 Basic Model Results

Table 3. Basic model regression analysis results

	Proxy Q = (1)	Proxy Q = (2)
Constant	2.70*** (19.99)	2.74*** (20.24)
HDER	0.05*** (3.97)	
NDER		-0.09* (-1.75)
EPS	0.05*** (31.49)	0.05*** (31.74)
DEV	0.00 (1.26)	0.00 (1.63)
GOV	0.08*** (11.88)	0.09*** (12.06)
SIZE	-0.15*** (-10.67)	-0.15*** (-10.64)
LEV	-0.62*** (-10.53)	-0.62*** (-10.55)
GROWN	0.01 (1.51)	0.01 (1.56)
Adj. R ²	0.2049	0.2032

Note: The value in () is t-value. The significant levels of 1%, 5% and 10% are expressed in ***, ** and * respectively.

Table 3 presents OLS regression results with firm value (Proxy Q) as the response variable, examining the HDER and NDER on firm value. In the first formula, the HDER coefficient is positive and significant at the 1% level, indicating that if a company tends to use derivatives as a hedging tool, it has a significant positive correlation with the company's value, which preliminarily supports the argument that "hedging can enhance corporate value." The second

formula shows that although the NDER coefficient is significantly negative, its significance is low and unstable. Therefore, it implies that companies engaging in speculative operations may need to bear higher risks, thus having a potential negative impact on corporate value. However, the significance level is relatively weak, which may indicate that the impact of speculative operations on corporate value is not widespread or susceptible to interference from other factors. In terms of control variables, EPS is positive and highly significant in all two equations, which is consistent with the positive relationship between profitability and corporate value generally found in existing literature, and the significance of GOV is the same; SIZE and LEV are negative in all two equations and significant at the 1% level, which means that although the increase in scale and leverage may expand the operational aspects, it may bring more agency risks or financial pressures in market evaluation, which will discount the company's value. The DEV and GROWN are not the main explanatory factors driving corporate value, and both are insignificant in the two equations.

4.3 Extended Model Results

Table 4. Extended model regression analysis results

	HDER = (3)	HDER = (4)
Constant	0.49*** (3.74)	0.11*** (3.24)
GOV	0.03*** (3.83)	-0.00 (-0.49)
EPS	0.01*** (3.85)	0.00*** (2.80)
DEV	0.01*** (8.54)	-0.00*** (-3.32)
SIZE	0.02 (1.35)	-0.01*** (-2.11)
LEV	-0.03 (-0.48)	-0.00 (-0.16)
GROWN	0.01 (0.82)	0.00 (0.38)
Adj. R ²	0.0236	0.0031

Note: The value in () is t-value. The significant levels of 1%, 5% and 10% are expressed in ***, ** and * respectively.

Table 4 uses an extended model to explore the determinants of companies' use of derivative financial products and conducts OLS regression analysis with two dependent variables: HDER and NDER. The results show that the coefficient of GOV in the model with HDER as the dependent variable is positive and reaches the 1% significance level, indicating that companies with more perfect governance mechanisms are more inclined to adopt hedging derivative strategies; in addition, in the NDER model, although the GOV coefficient is negative, it is not statistically significant, suggesting that the impact of corporate governance levels on speculative operations is less obvious. This phenomenon can also be explained by the fact that when internal supervision and external regulations are sounder, management is more likely to follow a prudent approach to reduce financial risks and maintain stable profits, but speculative operations are not generally suppressed (or encouraged). In addition, EPS is positive and

significant in both models, indicating that companies with better profitability have more resources or motivation to take positions in derivative products, regardless of whether their main purpose is to stabilize cash flow or pursue arbitrage. At the same time, DEV is positive and highly significant for hedging operations, and negative and significant for non-hedging operations, indicating that companies with larger deviations between control rights and cash flow rights are more inclined to adopt hedging strategies rather than engage in high-risk speculative positions; this result can be understood in the context of agency theory as highly concentrated control rights requiring a sound financial strategy to maintain or consolidate the long-term interests of the family (or major shareholders). As for SIZE, the coefficient is positive in the HDER model, but negative and significant in the NDER model, indicating that although larger companies have more resources to deal with financial risks, they are relatively less inclined to invest in speculative positions; the possible reason is that large companies are more susceptible to external supervision and market attention, and it is more difficult to conceal high-risk operations.

5. Conclusion

This study explores the impact of hedging and non-hedging purposes of derivative financial products on corporate value in Taiwan's listed companies. The study uses corporate value as the dependent variable of the combined cross-sectional data, with hedging and non-hedging purposes of derivative financial products as the main independent variables and combines corporate governance variables with multi-level regression analysis to verify the impact mechanism. The empirical results show that in terms of hedging operations, if a company uses derivatives for hedging purposes, the extent of its use is positively correlated with the company's value, which is consistent with theoretical expectations. That is, through hedging operations, enterprises can effectively reduce capital costs, reduce financial fluctuations, and stabilize profit flows, thereby gaining higher evaluations in the market and ultimately drive the increase in corporate value. Although this study was unable to directly test whether risk aversion transmits its impact specifically by reducing volatility, the positive relationship obtained has preliminarily supported the positive effect of risk aversion strategies.

Secondly, as far as non-risk-averse (speculative, arbitrage) operations are concerned, the empirical results are more complicated. When non-hedging is tested separately, its coefficient shows a negative effect, reaching significance in some models but not very stable, which is consistent with the theoretical expectation that speculative behavior may have a suppressive effect on corporate value due to factors such as high leverage risk and agency problems.

On the strategy of using derivatives, the results show that corporate governance positively explains risk aversion, that is, companies with sound governance mechanisms are more inclined to adopt a prudent risk aversion strategy. This finding supports the theoretical argument that "good governance can guide management to limit the use of derivatives to control risks." The impact of corporate governance on speculative operations of derivative financial products is negative but not significant. In addition, this study found that the positive impact of corporate governance on corporate value can be partly explained by the use of derivative financial products for hedging purposes, that is, corporate governance affects corporate value, and the impact is partly due to the use of derivative financial products for hedging purposes.

The findings of this study have substantial reference value for corporate financial decision-making and supervision mechanisms. If the results of this study can be appropriately used in the future and combined with institutional planning and supervision mechanisms, it will help the industry, government and academia to promote the long-term development of the market

and corporate management.

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